

Distributed Continual Learning enabled Multi-Head Attention based Deep Belief Gradient Model for COVID-19 Prediction with Medical Data

¹Roshan K. Ambatkar, ²Dr. Ashish B. Sasankar

^{*1}Research Scholar, Department of Electronics and Computer Science

Rashtrasant Tukadoji Maharaj Nagpur University, Nagpur Maharashtra, India

ambatkar.roshan@gmail.com

²Principal, Indraprasth New Arts, Commerce and Science College Wardha, Maharashtra, India

ashishdigital14@gmail.com

Abstract

The COVID-19 epidemic has impacted various financial and healthcare sectors. Nevertheless, they are suboptimal, thereby necessitating the employment of advanced Artificial Intelligence (AI) based techniques to facilitate timely diagnosis. Conventional methods fail in acquiring climate and region-specific epidemiological factors, which are mandatory in implementing detection models. To address this concern, the research exhibits a Distributed Continual Learning enabled Multi-Head Attention based Deep Belief Gradient model (DCL-MHA-DBG) to forecast COVID-19 cases based on the climate and region-wise transmission rate, growth rate, and spread rate of the disease. The parallel operation of the Deep Belief Networks (DBN) along with the Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM) enabled effective utilization of resources, while Multi-Head Attention improved selective focus. Considering the recovery rate based on the Tamil Nadu region, the model achieved significant outcomes with a correlation of 0.92, MAE OF 0.34, MAPE of 0.80%, MSE of 0.46, R^2 value of 0.84, and R^2 error value of 0.16, signifying progression over COVID-19 prediction tasks.

Keywords: COVID-19, Deep Learning, Epidemiological factors, Continual learning, Machine Learning.

1. Introduction

The Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19), first reported in late 2019, was caused by the Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2). It is an ultimately malicious disease that rapidly extends to around 200 nations in a short span. To face this issue, the World Health Organization (WHO) reported it as an epidemic, leading to various impacts [6].

Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA), Linear Regression, Logistic Regression, and Multiple Linear Regression, are utilized. However, these models encompass non-stationary data and non-linear components, causing complexities like inability to handle linear correlations, complex data extraction processes, and limited variable sets [19][20][21][8]. However, the traditional ML and

DL based approaches are affected by data complexity and high dimensionality issues. Moreover, they require large computational time and power to process the data, which could delay the treatment [1]. For instance, the Bidirectional Long, Short-Term Memory (LSTM) is utilized in pandemic prediction models. However, the interpretability of the DL model causes black box issues [22][5]. The optimization algorithms provide solutions to the conventional feature extraction and selection methods. Nevertheless, they rely on greedy and heuristic approaches, resulting in performance deficiency [23][1].

The drawbacks of the conventional prediction approaches are resolved by the DCL-MHA-DBG model, which enhances the input data quality by eliminating the unnecessary columns and attributes in the data. The missing data issue is overcome by the usage of the KNN imputation technique, which accurately imputes the missing data points. The complexities while processing the data are rectified by the utilization of continual learning, which splits the data sequentially while retaining the information obtained at the previous tasks. Further, the forecasting of COVID-19 cases is handled by the DCL-MHA-DBG model, and the key aspect of the work is depicted below.

- **Distributed Continual Learning enabled Multi-Head Attention-based Deep Belief Gradient model (DCL-MHA-DBG):** The utilization of Multi-Head Attention (MHA) allows the model to concentrate on needed aspects, thereby reducing computational loads before entering the regressors. The parallelization of the two predictive methods, DBN and GBM, increased progression by leveraging their combined strengths, like layer-wise processing and concurrent computation. The employment of distributed computing of parallelized modules improved scalability, resolved data complexities, with increased accuracy.

The subsequent sections of the article are constructed in this regard. Section 2 provides a review of conventional methods, their advantages and challenges, and the problem statement. Section 3 explains the system model along with the pictorial representation. Section 4 describes the proposed method and its operations in the COVID-19 case forecasting. Section 5 provides the results of the experimentation and concludes with the future works in Section 6.

2. Literature Review

The methodologies, advantages, and drawbacks of the related articles are mentioned below. Patra, P.S.K., and Tripathy, B. [1] introduced an Optimal Iterative COVID-19 Classification Network (OICC-Net) using ML and DL methods. The Random Forest Infused Particle Swarm-based Black Widow Optimization algorithm is utilized to acquire disease-related patterns from the dataset, and the 1-Dimensional Convolutional Neural Network (1D-CNN) is utilized for prediction. The ARIMA-DQN significantly improved the cost-efficiency and flexibility of the model. The limitation of this approach is that the acquired data could be affected by external variables.

Zheng, H.L. *et al.* [5] developed an interpretable data-driven ensemble framework enrolling three ML classifiers for the prediction of COVID-19. Moreover, three linear ensemble models were incorporated to integrate the results of the classifiers. The optimized LAD ensemble performed better than the base learners. However, they are prone to overfitting issues. Yang, W. and Chang, X., *et al.* [6] designed a composite prediction model based on LSTM and Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) named LSTM-GRU. The complexities in capturing non-linear patterns and persistent relationships in data are resolved by LSTM.

Khammash, E.H. *et al.* [7] designed an enhanced model utilizing various machine learning models to forecast COVID-19 in differing geographical regions. The Binary particle swarm optimization (BPSO) is employed for the selection of features. The Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM) outperformed other algorithms in high-altitude geographical areas, and the Random Forest (RF) algorithm outperformed other approaches by means of sea-level areas. The limitation of this approach is the lack of data relevant to each geographical region. Utku, A.,

2.1. Challenges

The drawbacks and limitations faced by the traditional models are mentioned as follows,

- The iterative mechanism of the 1D-CNN model [1] captured diverse temporal data patterns and features. However, the model lacked real-world integration for continuous monitoring.
- The ARIMA-DQN approach [2] resolved linearity complications and significantly improved flexibility and cost-efficiency. Regardless, the acquired data could be affected by external variables.
- The DFDNM model [4] effectively handled the vanishing gradient and exploding gradient problems using dense shortcut connections, but still, they led to high computational operation costs.
- The LSTM-GRU mechanism [6] outperformed cutting-edge methods in capturing temporal dependencies and precise predictions. Nevertheless, they lack optimization mechanisms and pose scalability issues.
- The hybrid CNN-LSTM approach [8] accomplished efficient feature engineering and captured district patterns. However, the model lacked sophisticated algorithms to process the input data.

2.2 Problem Statement

The COVID-19 pandemic caused serious impacts on the economic and medical sectors worldwide. Predicting COVID-19 cases across different regions and climatic patterns is complicated by the variability in the spread and recovery rate of the disease. To overcome this, the research develops a prediction model using a DL model with the COVID-19 Open Data repository, which contains climate-wise COVID-19-related attributes collected from different regions. Originally, the input data for the model is depicted as,

$$B = \langle \chi_{k-d}, \dots, \chi_{k-2}, \chi_{k-1}, \chi_k \rangle \quad (1)$$

where, B denotes the dataset, d indicates the number of days used as the time lag, k refers to the current time period, χ_k represents the k^{th} time at which data χ is created. Here χ_k can be further represented as,

$$\chi_k = \{c_{k,1}, \dots, c_{k,w}\} \quad (2)$$

Here, $c_{k,w}$ indicates the w^{th} COVID-19-related attribute in the k^{th} time period. Rather than simply predicting the COVID-19-affected cases, the forecasting of future events using epidemiological indicators such as disease transmission rate, growth rate, and recovery rate assists professionals in making informed decisions. Therefore, the model is trained based on the three epidemiological indicators, and the construction of these indicators is represented as,

3. System Model

The core purpose of the research is to predict the COVID-19 disease by determining the growth rate, recovery rate, and transmission rate of COVID-19 cases. The required regional data is constructed through various sources such as authoritative sources, crowdsourcing, and general sources. Moreover, climate-based analysis encompassing winter, summer, and monsoon is considered based on month-based splits to improve the handling of data. The aggregated data usually contains fluctuations like noise factors, redundancies, and information that is not necessary for the procedure. Similarly, the dataset often encompasses several missing values or attributes. To alleviate these issues, data preprocessing is initiated to clean and structure the data while retaining important information. The preprocessed outcome is utilized in the prediction model to forecast COVID-19 cases accurately by analyzing the region-wise epidemiological indicators. Figure 1 demonstrates the proposed architecture's system model.

Figure 1. System Model

4. Proposed Distributed Continual Learning enabled Multi-Head Attention based Deep Belief Gradient model for COVID-19 prediction

The central focus of the DCL-MHA-DBG model is the forecasting of COVID-19 based on both climate-wise and region-wise Transmission rate, Recovery rate, and Growth rate of the disease. Originally, the COVID-19 Open Data repository [24] was employed to acquire the input data, which includes information and attributes related to the COVID-19 cases in certain regions. The data samples often contain irrelevant entries, noise factors, redundant entries, missing data, and other inconsistencies. To alleviate this, a data preprocessing phase, encompassing the K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) imputation mechanism, is employed. KNN imputes relevant data points to the missing area, thereby increasing the data functionality. After preprocessing, the data is fed to the DCL-MHA-DBG model to perform predictions based on the three epidemiological indicators. The Continual Learning mechanism is employed to avoid catastrophic forgetting and computational complexities. The distributed learning of the GBM and DBN model combines the collective strengths of both mechanisms, thereby reducing complexities and enhancing scalability. Further, the Multi-Head Attention (MHA) is utilized to improve contextual understanding of the data by capturing long-term dependencies. The model is constructed thrice to forecast predictions for the three epidemiological indicators. Figure 2 demonstrates the block diagram of the proposed DCL-MHA-DBG model.

Figure 2. Block diagram of the proposed DCL-MHA-DBG model

4.1 Input Data Collection

Several related approaches for the prediction of COVID-19 suffer from generalization problems, which arise as a consequence of a lack of diversity or limited data. Therefore, the DCL-MHA-DBG model aggregates data from the Covid-19 Open Data [24], which contains various regional COVID-19 cases and related attributes, constructed between a specific time period. The representation for the input data is provided in equations (1) and (2).

The collected data encompassing COVID-19 cases and related attributes of dimension $[N, 708]$, is delivered to the preprocessing stage.

4.2 Data Preprocessing

Data pre-processing is the process of cleaning and preparing the time-series input data for further procedures of disease prediction. The presence of irrelevant data and unwanted attributes tampers with the efficiency of the model in forecasting COVID-19 cases. Thus, the pre-processing procedure removes all the inconsistencies from the input data χ_k , thereby increasing the model performance. The preprocessed data after the removal of irrelevant entities is represented as H , with a dimension $[N, 131]$, which is forwarded to the process of missing data imputation to handle the missing values.

4.3 Missing Data Imputation based on KNN

After the unnecessary components from the data are removed, the model undergoes data imputation using the KNN to estimate the missing values in the preprocessed outcome H . Initially, the missing variables are imputed by determining a set of nearest neighbors and parameters using the Euclidean distance measure. The process is mathematically depicted as,

$$g(u, v) = \sqrt{\sum_{f=1}^r (u_f - v_f)^2} \quad (8)$$

Here, $g(u, v)$ denotes the Euclidean distance, r indicates the dimension of the data, f represents the data attribute where, $f = 1, 2, 3, \dots, r$, u_f depicts the value from the f attribute covering the missing data, and v_f denotes the value from the f attribute covering the complete data. Subsequently, the missing data is determined by estimating the weighted mean of u_f , which is represented as,

4.4 Distributed Continual Learning enabled Multi-Head Attention based Deep Belief Gradient model for the prediction of COVID-19

The DCL-MHA-DBG model encompasses several ML approaches to facilitate effective forecasting of COVID-19 cases. Initially, the missing value imputed outcome I of size $[N, 131]$ is forwarded to the DCL-MHA-DBG model. While processing large non-stationary time-series data, learning models usually experience issues like catastrophic forgetting, where they radically forget previously learned information while working with new information. To alleviate this, the continual learning technique is implemented. Continual learning splits up the dataset into multiple tasks, considering the class labels. The resultant sliced data is denoted as W , which is fed over multiple modules where two individual prediction models, namely, DBN and GBM, each integrating an MHA mechanism, and combined by distributed learning, are implemented.

The forthcoming sections illustrate the working of each mechanism along with its integration using distributed modelling.

4.4.1 Distributed Learning

The data obtained after continual learning W , is too massive to be assimilated into the memory. In such scenarios, optimizers are operated based on batch sizes. Nevertheless, they face drawbacks like the implication of false gradients during training. To initiate a more comprehensive and accurate distribution of the dataset, data parallelism is initiated. The core concept of distributed learning is to facilitate synchronous model training similar to the mirrored strategy. In the mirrored strategy, the model is duplicated into multiple sections, where each section operates on a specific subset of the data. Each section calculates the gradients on its local batches [27][28]. In the proposed model aspect, the sections are replaced by several modules that operate concurrently. The outcome of the continual learning W_1 , where $W_1 \subseteq W$, is initially fed over two concurrently working MHA mechanisms, where the output of one MHA is allowed in the GBM and another in the DBN. The functioning of MHA is provided in the subsequent sections.

4.4.2 Multi-Head Attention

MHA is utilized to carry out multiple linear transformations on the input vector to obtain selective and comprehensive information. In sequential data, MHA specializes in capturing long-term dependencies. Attention is usually applied before prediction models to suppress the input by concentrating on the needed aspects, thereby reducing the computational burden. MHA is computed by determining the scaled dot product attention, where the input contains values of dimension $\sqrt{b_z}$, and keys and queries of dimension $\sqrt{b_y}$. The dot products of the keys and queries are computed and applied with the SoftMax function to acquire the weights of the values. During calculation, all the query vectors are combined in the matrix x , all the key vectors in the matrix y , and the value vectors in the matrix z . Scaled dot product attention is scientifically denoted as,

$$SDP_{att}(x, y, z) = SoftMax\left(\frac{xy^T}{\sqrt{b_y}}\right)z \quad (10)$$

Here, SDP_{att} illustrates the scaled dot product attention, x indicates the query matrix, y depicts the key matrix, z represents the value matrix, T denotes the transpose operation, and $\sqrt{b_y}$ depicts the dimension of the key vector. MHA is determined by implementing the scaled dot product attention concurrently using multiple heads. The computation of the head values is scientifically depicted as,

$$MHA(x, y, z) = concat(head_1, head_2, \dots, head_e)\tilde{J} \quad (12)$$

where, \tilde{J} represents the weight parameter [29]. In MHA, each attention heads centralize specific aspects of the input, whereas the outcome provides a multi-perspective representation of the input data. Here, two MHAs are operated in a distributed way, in which the result of the first MHA is indicated as t_1 , which is passed to the GBM, while the outcome of the second MHA t_2 is fed to the DBN. The pictorial demonstration of MHA is provided in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Multi-Head Attention

4.4.3 Gradient Boosting Machine

The outcome t_1 is allowed in the GBM to initiate predictions. GBM combines multiple weak learners and operates them iteratively to determine the best learner. The weighted data is obtained from the predictions of each learner and is utilized to train the subsequent weak learner. A major advantage of GBM is its ability to process complex heterogeneous data. The final prediction in GBM is determined by,

$$D(s) = \sum_{l=1}^L U_l \delta(s; V_l) \tag{13}$$

Here, $D(s)$ denotes the final learner, L depicts the maximum iterations performed, $\delta()$ indicates the feature vector function, V denotes the parameter, and U_i represents the coefficient for the i^{th} weak learner [30]. The empirical loss or error value is necessary to determine the weighted data in the predictions of each learner. GBM employs Mean Absolute Error (MAE) as the function to identify the error value of the predicted outcome and the true outcome. The lessening of errors while training improves the capacity of the model in predicting the classes correctly, thus improving overall prediction accuracy. The mathematical equation for MAE calculation is,

$$MAE = \sum_{j=1}^o \frac{|E_j - \hat{E}_j|}{o} \tag{14}$$

where, o denotes the maximum observations, E_j indicates the true outcome, and \hat{E}_j indicates the obtained outcome. The output of the GBM mechanism is denoted as E_1 . Figure 4 demonstrates the architecture of GBM.

Figure 4. Gradient Boosting Machine

4.4.4 Deep Belief Network

While the outcome t_1 is processed in the GBM model, the outcome t_2 from the second MHA layer is allowed to be processed in the DBN model simultaneously. DBN is a generative graphical method that involves the connection of multiple independently trained Restricted Boltzmann Machines (RBM). RBM comprises two layers, where the first visible layer takes the input data while the second hidden layer extracts underlying patterns and captures higher-order correlations. The training of the entire DBN model can lead to computational complexities; hence, a layer-wise unsupervised learning strategy, along with fine-tuning, is stimulated. Initially, the parameters are fixed, and the input vector is obtained to train the RBM separately. The outcomes of the first RBM are applied as the input to the subsequent RBM, and the process is followed iteratively throughout the network [31]. Finally, a Feed Forward Neural Network is employed to perform predictions based on the probabilistic distribution of the RBM. The mathematical equation for DBN is denoted as,

$$p(q) = \sum_{\beta} (p(\beta | C) p(q | \beta, C)) \quad (15)$$

where, β denotes the hidden layer, C indicates the weight, q denotes the visible layer, and $p()$ denotes the probabilistic function [32]. The function employed to determine the error values in the DBN model is Mean Squared Error (MSE). The scientific equation to calculate the MSE value is,

$$MSE = \frac{1}{o} \cdot \sum_{j=1}^o (E_2 - \hat{E}_2)^2 \tag{16}$$

where, E_2 indicates the true outcome, \hat{E}_2 indicates the obtained outcome, and o indicates the total number of observations. The visual representation of DBN is provided in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Deep Belief Network

5. Results and Discussion

The demonstration and justification of the experimental results achieved by the DCL-MHA-DBG method under several performance metrics and statistical validations are illustrated in this section.

5.1 Experimental Setup

The experimentation for the DCL-MHA-DBG model is executed in Windows 11 with system specifications of 16 GB RAM and 128 GB ROM, encompassing an Intel i7-13770K processor and an Nvidia GeForce RTX 3080 Ti graphics card with 12GB GPU Memory. The Python 3.8 tool, along with PyCharm Community Edition IDE, is utilized for implementation. The hyperparameters for the DCL-MHA-DBG model are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Hyperparameters

Hyperparameters		
GBM	Number of estimators	300
	Learning rate	0.1
	Random state	23
	Maximum depth	1
DBN	Number of nodes in each hidden layer	256
	Number of hidden layers	2
	Learning rate	0.1
	Batch size	32
	Dropout	0.2
	Activation	ReLU

5.2 Dataset Description

To perform COVID-19 case forecasting based on region-wise and climate-wise epidemiological indicators, the DCL-MHA-DBG model employs the Covid-19 Open Data [24] that encompasses multiple data attributes related to COVID-19 disease. The description for the dataset is provided below.

Covid-19 Open Data: The COVID-19 Open Data repository contains a comprehensive collection of contemporary COVID-19-based data. The repository aggregates rich information from over 20,000 locations globally, thus assisting researchers, data scientists, public health sectors, and policy makers in studying and controlling the virus. Some attributes present in the dataset include COVID-19 cases, hospitalizations, vaccination rates, deaths, and others. Major sources of data aggregation include authoritative sources like universities, governments, and hospitals, crowdsourcing, and general sources such as publications and media. Figure 7 depicts the visualization of a few data attributes from the mentioned dataset.

Figure 7. Data attribute visualization from the Covid-19 Open Data Repository

5.3 Evaluation Metrics

The functioning of the DCL-MHA-DBG method is assessed with various metrics, including Correlation, MSE, MAE, Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), R-squared (R^2), and R^2 error. The formulation of each metric is given in Table 2.

Table 2. Performance metrics

Metrics	Formulation
MSE	$X_{mse} = \frac{1}{o} \cdot \sum_{j=1}^o (K_j - \hat{K}_j)^2$ <p>where, X_{mse} represents the MSE metric, K_j indicates the actual value, \hat{K}_j indicates the predicted value, and o indicates the number of observations.</p>
MAE	$X_{mae} = \sum_{j=1}^o \frac{ K_j - \hat{K}_j }{o}$ <p>where, X_{mae} depicts the MAE metric.</p>
MAPE	$X_{mape} = \frac{1}{o} \sum_{j=1}^o \left \frac{K_j - \hat{K}_j}{K_j} \right \times 100$ <p>where, X_{mape} indicates the MAPE metric.</p>
R ²	$X_{r-sq} = 1 - \frac{\sum_{j=1}^o (K_j - \hat{K}_j)^2}{\sum_{j=1}^o (K_j - \bar{K})^2}$ <p>where, X_{r-sq} denotes the R² metric, and \bar{K} indicates the mean of the actual value</p>
Correlation	$X_{cor} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^o (K_j - \bar{K})(\hat{K}_j - \bar{K})}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^o (K_j - \bar{K})^2 \sum_{j=1}^o (\hat{K}_j - \bar{K})^2}}$ <p>where, X_{cor} represents the correlation value.</p>

5.4 Experimental Results

Figure 8 illustrates the experimental results for the proposed model based on growth rate analysis with climate conditions.

Figure 8. Growth rate analysis based on Climate

5.5 Comparative Methods

Traditional methods, including 1D-CNN [1], ARIMA-DQN [2], LSTM [3], DFDNM [4], LSTM-GRU [6], and DBN-GBM, are employed with the proposed DCL-MHA-DBG model to display the model's progression in predicting COVID-19 cases. The subsequent sections provide a comparative valuation of the DCL-MHA-DBG model in contrast to the related models based on both climate and region.

5.5.1 Comparative Analysis based on Climate

The following subsections describe the comparative valuation of the DCL-MHA-DBG model over the conventional methods based on the climate-wise epidemiological indicators, including growth rate, recovery rate, and transmission rate. The seasons considered for the analysis include summer, winter, monsoon, and post-monsoon.

a) Analysis based on growth rate

Figure 14 demonstrates the comparative assessment of the DCL-MHA-DBG model over the conventional methods in accordance with the growth rate. Grounding the summer season, DCL-MHA-DBG achieved a correlation value of 0.91, which is relatively higher than related methods such as the DBN-GBM method with 0.75, ARIMA-DQN with 0.75, 1D-CNN with 0.76, LSTM with 0.78, LSTM-GRU with 0.86, and DFDNM with 0.90. Similarly, DCL-MHA-DBG achieved significant outcomes with 0.42, 0.82%, 0.56, 0.84, and 0.16 for metrics such as MAE, MAPE, MSE, R^2 , and R^2 error, respectively.

Figure 14. Analysis of growth rate based on climate

Table 3. Statistical Analysis for the DCL-MHA-DBG model

		Methods vs Obtained Results	Climate-wise						
			DBN-GBM	ARIM A-DQN	1D-CNN	LSTM	LSTM-GRU	DFDN M	DCL-MHA-DBG
Growth Rate	Correlation	<i>Best</i>	0.78	0.81	0.82	0.83	0.86	0.90	0.91
		<i>Mean</i>	0.77	0.79	0.80	0.81	0.84	0.86	0.88
		<i>Variance</i>	0.0001	0.0006	0.0007	0.0004	0.0002	0.0004	0.0007
		<i>Standard Deviation</i>	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.03
		<i>T-statistics</i>	2.21	2.91	2.81	2.60	2.15	1.46	1.89
		<i>P-value</i>	0.11	0.06	0.07	0.08	0.12	0.24	0.15
			Methods vs Obtained Results	Region-wise					
				DBN-GBM	ARIM A-DQN	1D-CNN	LSTM	LSTM-GRU	DFDN M
	Correlation	<i>Best</i>	0.81	0.82	0.83	0.85	0.89	0.89	0.92
		<i>Mean</i>	0.76	0.77	0.81	0.83	0.86	0.88	0.90
		<i>Variance</i>	0.0010	0.0010	0.0003	0.0002	0.0002	0.0001	0.0002
		<i>Standard Deviation</i>	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02
<i>T-statistics</i>		1.89	1.67	2.59	1.81	1.63	2.43	2.78	
<i>P-value</i>		0.16	0.19	0.08	0.17	0.20	0.09	0.07	

5.7 Comparative Discussion

Early forecasting of COVID-19 cases is essential to initiate both proactive and reactive measures and prompt treatment.

Conventional prediction approaches, such as 1D-CNN [1], obtained prominent outcomes in disease prediction. Similarly, the ARIMA-DQN method [2] issued accurate predictions, but its capacity is limited as it uses historical data without external variables for predictions. The LSTM-based model [3] provided meaningful insights into the The hybrid LSTM-GRU technique [6] excelled in capturing temporal dependencies and outperformed several models with precise predictions. However, they are prone to scalability issues. The baseline GBM-DBN model is not comprehensive as it lacks attention mechanisms and parallelization to overcome complexities with resources and computation. The aforementioned inconsistencies can be successfully alleviated by the proposed DCL-MHA-DBG model, as it incorporates continual learning and distributed learning mechanisms to resolve computational complexities while processing huge amounts of sequential data. The parallelization and ensemble of the GBM and DBM model, along with the MHA mechanism, helps focus on all factors and attributes related to the disease. Specifically, the employment of MHA resolves overfitting and improves generalization. The complexities emerging with the data are resolved with the usage of the Covid-19 Open Data repository, which contains both historical data and external variables related to the disease. Tables 4 and 5 illustrate the performance comparison of the DCL-MHA-DBG model over related methods with the growth rate based on the summer season and the recovery rate in the Tamil Nadu region, respectively.

Table 4. Comparative discussion of the DCL-MHA-DBG model based on growth rate in the summer season

Methods vs Obtained Results		Growth Rate							
		DBN- GBM	ARIMA- DQN	1D- CNN	LSTM	LSTM- GRU	DFDNM	DCL-MHA- DBG	
Climate wise	Summer Season	Correlation	0.75	0.75	0.76	0.78	0.86	0.90	0.91
		MAE	1.80	1.55	1.01	0.87	0.69	0.46	0.42
		MAPE	2.73	2.04	1.93	1.47	1.39	1.08	0.82
		MSE	1.99	1.69	1.12	1.05	0.86	0.58	0.56
		R^2 error	0.44	0.44	0.43	0.38	0.25	0.19	0.16
		R^2	0.56	0.56	0.57	0.62	0.75	0.81	0.84

Table 5. Comparative discussion of the DCL-MHA-DBG model based on the recovery rate in the Tamil Nadu region

Methods vs Obtained Results		Recovery Rate							
		DBN- GBM	ARIMA- DQN	1D- CNN	LSTM	LSTM- GRU	DFDNM	DCL- MHA- DBG	
Region wise	Tamil Nadu	Correlation	0.75	0.77	0.80	0.87	0.88	0.88	0.92
		MAE	1.67	1.21	1.08	0.70	0.44	0.39	0.34
		MAPE	2.34	2.00	1.89	1.58	1.17	0.92	0.80
		MSE	1.82	1.35	1.27	0.87	0.57	0.56	0.46
		R ² error	0.44	0.40	0.35	0.25	0.22	0.22	0.16
		R ²	0.56	0.60	0.65	0.75	0.78	0.78	0.84

6. Conclusion

The DCL-MHA-DBG model, utilized for the forecasting of COVID-19 cases, encompassing both climate-wise and region-wise transmission rate, growth rate, and recovery rate, excels in forecasting even in complicated scenarios. The usage of KNN imputation during preprocessing enhanced overall functionality by resolving the missing data issues and retaining the required data. The continual learning approach used in the model resolved catastrophic gradient issues and improved generalizability while processing large amounts of data. The concurrent implementation of the GBM and DBN enhanced the overall prediction abilities of the model by leveraging their combined benefits. The usage of MHA above each individual regressor reduced computation loads while focusing on the necessary aspects. The utilization of distributed learning reduced training time and computational burdens, thereby contributing to flexibility and overall model efficiency. The model is implemented three times to forecast the transmission rate, recovery rate, and growth rate of the COVID-19 cases. For region-wise forecasting based on recovery rate, DCL-MHA-DBG achieved a correlation of 0.92, MAPE of 0.80%, MAE of 0.34, MSE of 0.46, R² value of 0.84, and R² error value of 0.16. Future work involves the consideration of more regions to further enhance diversity and the usage of hybrid metaheuristic algorithms to fine-tune the hyperparameters.

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